

BioAgora T1.1 updated workshop guideline

22 November 2022

Timing	Topic	Who	Content/Facilitator questions
12.00-12.05	Welcome	Eszter	explaining the wsh and the T1.1 methodological approach to the audience
12.05-12.20	Presentation	Attila	Conceptual categorization of challenges that limit the implementation of the BDS2030 - presentation based on the literature review
12.20-12.35	Q&A	Attila + Eszter	questions and comments from the audience (Eszter facilitates the dialogue)
12.35-13.15	Break-out groups	Eszter, Attila, Karmen, Carla, Marie, +Juliette if needed	<p>The break-out groups focus on how the demonstration cases and the other WPs of Bioagora will link back to the BDS 2030. The project's main aim is to ratchet up the BDS 2030, so how this can be done, taken into consideration the implementation challenges identified so far. Support document: flipchart incl. one row from the large table (1 BDS objective X 8 challenge categories, with input to the cells). Facilitating questions for the break-out groups on demonstration cases:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) First, find a volunteer who can act as a rappporteur in the WP1 session on the second day. 2) Look at the excerpt from the table and think about the identified challenges. Is there any other challenge you would like to add or refine? If so, please add it by using a post-it note. Max. 10 minutes. 3) Facilitators take a picture about the table with post-its 4) Now group these post-its according to how far the demonstration case can address each of these challenges. On the flipchart there will be three concentric circles. Inner circle: challenges definitely addressed by the demo case. Middle circle: challenges that might be addressed by the demo case. Outer circle: challenges that are definitely beyond the demo case. People can put post-its into the right circle. Try to achieve consensus. Max. 20 minutes 5) In the last 10 minutes, please try to formulate key research questions for the demo case, taken into account the challenges that you put into the two central circles. 6) Before leaving the break-out group, be sure that there is one rapporteur in your group, who will sum up the work of the break-out group on the second day (WP1 session). The rapporteur / group can think further the research question during the coffee breaks/dinner if they wish so.

Break-out groups (people join the groups based on their expertise):

- Group 1 (Eszter): **Pollination** demonstration case – BDS 2030 objective on **bringing nature back to agricultural land**.
- Group 2 (Carla): **Freshwater** demonstration case – BDS 2030 objective on **freshwater ecosystems**.
- Group 3 (Karmen): **Nature-based solutions** demonstration case – BDS 2030 objective on **urban and peri-urban areas**.
- Group 4 (Attila): **CBD** demonstration case – BDS 2030 objective on **raising the level of ambition and commitment** worldwide.

Notes from the break-out groups

Group 1: Pollination

=> POLLIN

CH1: IMPLEMENT IN MULTILEVEL GOV. FRM

LAND PROPERTY SYSTEM & LAND CONCENTRATION & ACCESSIBILITY
 LARGE DISPARITIES AMONG MEMBER STATES/REGIONS (ECOLOGICAL STATUS, FARM SIZE, INTEREST ETC.)
 HIGH ADMINISTRATIVE COMPLEXITY OF AGRY-ENVIRONMENTAL SCHEMES
 TRANSLATING THE FARMER POLICY STRATEGY TO NATIONAL LEGISLATION IS TIME CONSUMING

CH2: NON-SYSTEMATIC PLANNING

COST EFFECTIVENESS OF CONSERVATION MEASURES CAN BE IMPROVED BY MORE SYSTEMATIC PLANNING
 UNANTICIPATED INDIRECT IMPACTS: EG. NO HERBICIDES = MORE HERBIVORE INSECTS = SOIL DEGRADATION

Start with thinking about the existing situation

CH3: MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

NATURA 2000 MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS TO BE INTEGRATED TO RURAL DEVELOPMENT PLANS
 ECOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL CHALLENGES OF SEMI-SUBSISTENCE AREAS & FLEXIBLE POLICIES NEEDED

Nature Directives do not apply to farmers?

CH4: STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION

UNEVEN LEVEL OF TRUST AND SOCIAL CAPITAL AMONG FARMERS & BETWEEN FARMERS AND PUBLIC AUTHORITIES
 POLICY IMPLEMENTATION DEPENDS ON FARMERS' WILLINGNESS TO PARTICIPATE IN AGRY-ENV. SCHEMES

Central role of both in removing power concentration in farm systems, bringing more resources in

Endorsing the presence of existing measures in rural areas

Stakeholder choices about diet and consumption habits

CH5: FUNDING

INSUFFICIENT FUNDING FOR CAP PILLAR 2 AECMs
 FOOD SECURITY AND AGRI. PRODUCTION STAND OVER CONSERVATION OBJECTIVES (N2000 AND OTHERS)

CH6: LIMITS TO EU GLOBALIZATION

BETTER KNOWLEDGE FOR PRODUCTION RISK BY FARMERS
 BETTER DISTRIBUTION OF COSTS ALONG VALUE CHAIN (less in labor middle)
 A PROPORTION OF PRODUCTION RISK PROBABLY NOT COVERED

Reliance on our food system is important

CH7: AVAILABILITY OF KNOWLEDGE

TOO LITTLE KNOWLEDGE OF FUNCTIONAL AGROBIODIVERSITY IS NOT YET TRANSLATED TO MUST PRACTICES
 SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE ON FUNCTIONAL AGROBIODIVERSITY IS NOT YET TRANSLATED TO MUST PRACTICES

Measuring the impact of agri-environmental schemes

More understanding how productivity and quality is linked to environmental sustainability

CH8: HORIZONTAL POLICY COHERENCE

LACK OF POLICY COHERENCE: POLICY OBJECTIVES WITHOUT CONCRETE GUIDANCE ON IMPLEMENTATION
 POLITICAL PRESSURE BY STRONG INTEREST GROUPS mostly Council & Parliament

AGRI-BASED CAP PILLAR 2 MEASURES ARE NOT FULLY AVAILABLE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

Moving from a CAP PILLAR 2 to a CAP PILLAR 1 to a CAP PILLAR 3

Pressure on the environment in agriculture industry

"Food security" taken as absolute priority

Jessica Gandy
KIMBA KRAUZE
Sibille Schraer
Michael Adenauer

DANI VIMERO

No need coordinated management

CH1: IMPLEMENT IN MULTILEVEL GOV. FRAMEWORK

Multi-level vs POLICENTRIC

CH1+CH7
NO POLICY ON DRIVERS OF CHANGE ONLY ON IMPACT

LARGE PERCENTAGE OF THREATENED FRESHWATER SPECIES LIVES OUTSIDE OF RADIATION ZONE

STREAM RESTORATION PRACTICES/APPROACHES ARE NON-SYSTEMATIC AND NOT BASED ON EVIDENCE

RIVER FRAGMENTATION UNDERESTIMATED

LACKING MULTI-FUNCTIONAL IMPLEMENTATION OF PLVE
HABITAT DIVERSITY COLLECTIVE MANAGEMENT

CH2: NON-SYSTEMATIC PLANNING

CH3: MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

INSUFFICIENT MANAGEMENT INTENSITY OF PROTECTED AREA

NO REAL CATCHMENT APPROACH ESPECIALLY FOR CITIES AND CIST

NATURE RESTORATION PLAN PROPOSAL TO TAKE INTO CONSIDERATION

AND INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES

DIFFERENCES OF PERCEPTIONS OF DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

AGRICULTURAL STAKEHOLDERS ARE NOT AWARE/NEGLECT THEIR IMPACT ON FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS

Add Ecological services as a communication tool

ROLE NOT PARTICIPATION

RESTORATION'S REQUIREMENTS ARE NOT ASSESSED

Who are the actors? E.g. concrete companies

Need for local understanding/discussion
Need for independent assessment
Need for household understanding

Why? Who is to be blamed? Links between challenge? CH1-CH7

Who are the actors? E.g. concrete companies

CH4: STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION

GLOBAL ACTION PLAN

LINE WITH NBS AS ALTERNATIVE TO GREY INFRASTRUCTURE

Lack of economic value for BD

TELL COMPLIANCE NOT ADDRESSED SUFFICIENTLY IN IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Dependent of free (donor) money
- low eye does a restoration system need to be in long time to take effect

CH5: FUNDING

LACK OF FUNDS/RESOURCES FOR MONITORING FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS

REVENUE STREAMS

CH7: AVAILABILITY OF KNOWLEDGE

LOCAL/REGIONAL PRESSURES ON FRESHWATER BIODIV IS OFTEN UNKNOWN AND/OR MIXED

LACK OF ASSESSMENT OF GROSS UNDER IMPACTS OF FUNCTIONAL RESTORATION PROJECTS

MONITORING - LACK OF LONG-TERM MONITORING - GEOGRAPHIC AND TAXONOMIC BIAS

SCIENCE FOR CITIZENS and not for CITIZENS and/or policy

CH8: HORIZONTAL COOPERATION AND REFERENCE

TRADE-OFFS BETWEEN RENEWABLE ENERGY PROJECTS (DAMS) AND FRESHWATER BIODIV

UPPER LOAD INTENSIVE AGRICULTURE (WHICH IS OFTEN BY CAP PILLAR 1 PAYMENTS)

Economic interest of stakeholders

REFERENCE THEMSELVES E.G. INFRASTR. FUNDING IGNORES BD.

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What BioAgora will address

DIRECT link to transformative change

May

Indirect link

① Availability/ accessibility/ usability of knowledge to policy
• id of research gaps through work

④ Limitations to EU Biodiversity efforts

⑥ Non-Systemic planning

② Funding
• More relevant research funding
• Cost effectiveness
• + or - funding related to BD funding (PAFs)
→ Scientific + other

⑤ Management effectiveness

⑧ Stakeholder participation

⑦ Policy implementation in a multi-level governance framework

③ Horizontal Policy coherence
→ e.g. through cross-sectoral JCs

⑨ Power/interest dynamic
Vertical policy coherence
• Political will

Will not
No link

